

A large white number '45' is centered within a golden laurel wreath. The wreath is set against a dark blue background that features a faint, glowing DNA double helix structure. The overall design is celebratory and scientific.

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THE GENETICS SOCIETY OF NIGERIA
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PATHWAY TO FOOD SECURITY**

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GENETICS OF ALUMINUM TOLERANCE IN COWPEA ACCESSIONS SCREENED IN POTS UNDER THE FIELD CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

Aluminum toxicity is a major factor limiting crop productivity on acid soils, thus posing a challenge to food production. This study assessed the level of genetic diversity for aluminum tolerance in cowpea and the intercharacter association of important traits for the effective selection of tolerant genotypes. Ten accessions of the crop were screened in pots filled with topsoil employing a 10 x 4 factorial experiment in a completely randomized design. The aluminum treatments imposed were 0, 50, 100, and 200 μM AlCl_3 . Results revealed significant differences among accessions for all traits studied. Aluminum treatment imposed significant differences on all traits except seeds/plant and seed yield while the interaction was significant for all traits except emergence percentage and plant height. Heritability was high ($\geq 60\%$) for all traits except pods/plant (57.98%), and genetic advance as a percent of the mean was high ($\geq 20\%$) for all traits except days to flowering (11.08%) and plant height (15.87%). Biplot revealed that high seed yield under aluminum stress was directly associated with high seeds/plant, a higher number of roots/plant, and high root weight/plant while higher seeds/pod was a consequence of deeper root length, late flowering, higher root weight, and higher number of roots.

Key words: acidity, growth, heritability, toxicity, variability, yield

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INTRODUCTION

Excessive acidification of soils is a consequence of uninterrupted rigorous agriculture as well as the alteration of environmental conditions propelled by global climate change (Shetty *et al.*, 2021). Aluminum (Al) toxicity is a major factor limiting crop productivity on acid soils, thus limiting food production. When its concentration in soil surpasses 3 mg kg⁻¹ of soil at a pH of 5.5, its toxicity is manifested (Casierra-Posada *et al.*, 2021). Al inhibits root elongation in Al-sensitive plants as a consequence of its quick inhibition of cell division and cell expansion of root meristems (Phukunkamkaew *et al.*, 2021) and can also obstruct the uptake of minerals as well as water (Kochian, 1995). This can lead to serious drought stress and nutrient deficiency (Tang *et al.*, 2002).

Presently, 40% of the world's arable lands in many subtropical and tropical areas of the world (Phukunkamkaew *et al.*, 2021), and more than 50% of the world's potentially arable lands are acidic (Siecinska and Nosalewicz, 2016). In Nigeria, up to 18% of the total land area is acidic (Ajayi, 2021). The largest amount of cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* L. Walp) is produced in Nigeria which stands at 36% of the world's total (FAO, 2022). Nigeria belongs to the tropical belt where agriculture is largely practiced on acidic soils as semi-subsistence farming (Akinrinde *et al.*, 2006). Several agronomic strategies including the

application of lime and organic matter are employed by farmers for the management of acid soils to sustain yield. However, the impracticality of these soil improvement strategies in many regions lies in their high cost of deployment (Siecinska and Nosalewicz, 2016). Hence, as a cost-effective strategy, it is imperative to examine the source of aluminum tolerance present in the adapted crop species such as cowpea in Nigeria and other tropical regions of the world.

Several studies on Al tolerance in cowpea exist based on several agronomic and yield traits (Akinrinde *et al.*, 2006; Ajayi, 2021). However, information regarding the level of genetic diversity and character association in cowpea under aluminum stress is limited. To develop Al-tolerant genotypes of cowpea, a better understanding of the presence and magnitude of the genetic diversity for Al tolerance in a gene pool is important. Heritability of traits and their genetic gains are critical to successful breeding programs since the strengths of such estimates provide the extent to which improvement can be made while the association of important traits is useful for multiple selections of yield contributing traits (Ajayi *et al.*, 2014). In cognizance of the above, the present study assessed the level of genetic diversity for aluminum tolerance in cowpea and the

intercharacter association of important traits for the effective selection of Al-tolerant genotypes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The ten accessions involved had been previously screened under aluminum stress based on germination parameters (Ajayi, 2021) and are presented in Table 1. The location of the present study was the Plant Science and Biotechnology Experimental Field, Adekunle Ajasin University, Nigeria, and the period was between July and October 2016. The accessions were supplied by the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Nigeria.

This experiment was performed following a modified procedure from Ezeh et al. (2007). Six hundred bottom-perforated plastic pots (5L capacity) were filled each with topsoil collected near the experimental field (five pots per accession per treatment per replicate). The experimental field soil surface was covered with polythene before the arrangement of the plastic pots during the course of the experiment. Seeds were planted (after pre-planting soil analysis by spectrometry) in the pots each containing 3.5 kg of topsoil treated twice (at 1-week intervals) with 500 ml of 0, 50, 100, and 200 μM AlCl_3 in a completely randomized design with 3 replicates. Each accession was sown in pots at the rate of three seeds per pot with five pots per treatment per replicate and thinned to one plant per pot 10 days after emergence. Treatment application continued once per week until week 5 after planting (WAP).

Data collection

The emergence percentage was determined 10 days after planting (DAP). Plant height and the number of leaves were determined at 5 WAP. The number of days to first flowering was determined as plants flowered. Parameters such as the number of pods per plant, the number of seeds per pod, seed yield per plant, the number and length of main roots, and dry root weight were determined at maturity. The root parameters were determined by cutting the stem from the roots of the plants and carefully removing the soil from the roots by immersing the whole pot in a big bowl of water. After this, counting of the main roots was done and the length of the tap root was measured. The root dry weight was recorded after oven drying at 80°C to constant weights for 24 hrs.

Statistical analyses

Data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the GLM procedure of SPSS (version 20). Accessions were ranked based on

their level of tolerance to aluminum stress using the tolerance index (TI) calculated as $(X \times Y) / (\bar{X})^2$, where X was the mean performance of accession for a trait under the control treatment, and Y the average mean performance of accession for a trait under aluminum treatments, and $\bar{X}$ was the grand mean of all accessions for that trait under the control treatment. Accessions with mean TI greater than the grand mean of TI were deemed to be more tolerant while the ones with lower values were more susceptible. Estimates of genetic parameters were performed according to Ojo and Ayuba (2016) with modifications as follows: Error variance (V_E) = σ_E^2 = Mean square error (MS_E). Genotype $\times$ treatment variance (V_{GT}) = σ_{GT}^2 = $(MS_{GT} - MS_E)/r$. Genotypic variance (V_G) = σ_G^2 = $(MS_G - MS_E)/rT$. Phenotypic variance (V_P) = $V_G + V_{GT}/T + V_E/rT$. Genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV) = $\frac{\sqrt{V_G}}{\bar{X}} \times 100$. Phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV) = $\frac{\sqrt{V_P}}{\bar{X}} \times 100$. Broad-sense heritability (H^2) = $V_G / (V_G + (V_{GT}/T) + (V_E/rT))$. Genetic advance (GA) = $\frac{V_G}{\sqrt{V_P}} \times k$; $k = 2.06$ (selection differential). Genetic advance as percent of the mean (GAM) = $\frac{GA}{\bar{X}} \times 100$; where T , $\bar{X}$, and r are the number of treatments, grand mean of trait, and replicates, respectively. Genetic parameters were categorized as cited in Ajayi et al. (2014). Data were subjected to biplot analysis with paleontological statistics (PAST) version 4.01 for the estimates of genotype $\times$ character association.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The significant effect of accession revealed in the present study for all measured traits indicated the presence of a sufficient level of variations among the accessions under aluminium stress as reported by Ojo and Ayuba (2016). The significant effect of aluminium treatment for most traits indicated that the treatment was effective on the measured traits except for seeds per plant and seed yield per plant. The highly significant effect of accession $\times$ treatment on measured traits indicated that the response of accessions varied under different treatments (Villagarcia et al., 2001; Akinrinde and Neumann, 2006), except for emergence percentage and the number of days to first flowering (ANOVA Table not presented). In this regard, identification of accessions with high stability and superior yield across different levels of

aluminium stress would be important to maximizing yield and also useful for cowpea breeding programs for aluminium tolerance. Generally, aluminium treatment influenced all measured traits among the accessions; while inhibitory responses occurred in some traits, the effect was stimulatory in others. In traits such as emergence percentage, root length, and dry weight of roots, treatment of up to 50 – 200 μM , 100 – 200 μM , and 50 – 100 μM , respectively caused a significant reduction in the traits (Table 2). However, amongst traits with stimulatory effects due to aluminium stress, only the number of leaves per plant was significantly stimulated in plants treated to 100 - 200 μM . In the present study, responses to aluminium stress were accession dependent as described by Ezech *et al.* (2007) and Kushwaha *et al.* (2017) in cowpea.

Previous studies have reported information on the level of aluminum tolerance in cowpea and many other crop species. However, information regarding the genetic variability and character association of the crop under aluminum stress is scarce (Ojo and Ayuba, 2016). In the present study, the combination of high GCV and PCV obtained for traits such as the number of pods per plant, seeds per pod, seeds per plant, seed yield per plant, number of roots, root length, and dry weight of roots indicated that the accessions had a broad genetic base for these characters under aluminum stress. However, low PCV and GCV shown in plant height and days to first flowering suggested that these characteristics would be less responsive to improvement through selection (Table 3). These results agree with Ojo and Ayuba (2016) for yield, plant height, and root parameters as reported by Ojo *et al.* (2016). Little differences between GCV and PCV for most characters indicated a strong genetic effect on these characters. Moderate heritability in pods per plant and high heritability for other characters with moderate to high GAM indicated additive gene effects superiority (Singh *et al.*, 2022), and that the traits are effectively transmitted to the progeny, hence, selection for these traits will be effective for aluminum stress tolerance in cowpea for the tropical regions. These results are in agreement with the findings of Bianchi-Hall *et al.* (1998), Ogunbayo *et al.* (2014), and Ojo and Ayuba (2016) in soybean.

Tolerance indices (Table 4) based on all parameters were able to group accessions into different classes of tolerance: AC03, AC04, AC05, AC06, AC08, and AC09 were the highly tolerant accessions with above-average values for

all the aluminium tolerance indices. AC02 was moderately tolerant while AC01, AC10, and AC07 were the highly susceptible accessions. Notable differences existed among accessions for each of the tolerance indices as reported by Massot *et al.* (1992), Alamgir and Akhter (2009), and Roy and Bhadra (2014). Several aluminum tolerance indices have been found effective in the discrimination of different genotypes of crop species among which one of the best is the aluminum tolerance index based on root parameters (Hede *et al.*, 2002; Lisitsyn, and Amunova, 2015; Phukunkamkaew *et al.*, 2021).

Bi-plot analysis (Fig. 1) separated accessions according to their levels of tolerance. The first two PCs were used for the identification of important traits and their correlations. The GT biplot in the present study captured 75.90% of the variations due to genotype and genotype $\times$ trait interactions. The length of the trait vector projected from the origin shows the traits' ability to discriminate among accessions. Hence, important traits such as the number of seeds per pod, seed per plant, seed yield per plant, number of pods per plant, number of leaves, and all the root parameters were identified as influential traits for aluminum tolerance because they possessed longer vectors which gave them extraordinary discrimination powers. Conversely, traits such as plant height and emergence percentage were deemed as not important because of their short projection of vectors under aluminum stress.

The correlation between two traits is defined by the cosine of the angle between them (Atnaf *et al.*, 2017). Due to the acute angles observed among these traits' vectors, seed yield per plant was directly associated with higher seeds per plant, a higher number of roots, and a high dry weight of roots, and weakly correlated with seeds per pod, days to first flowering, and root length. This is an indication that the number of roots, seeds per plant, and dry weight of roots, as well as root length, seeds per pod, and higher number of days to flowering in cowpea plants, can be used to select high-yielding and tolerant plants under aluminum stress. A higher number of seeds per pod was directly related to deeper root length and late flowering under aluminum stress. This indicated that a deeper root system can be used to select tolerant, late-maturing genotypes with a higher number of seeds per pod under aluminum stress. However, a higher number of pods per plant was slightly associated with a higher number of leaves. Number of leaves was

negatively correlated with seed yield and all the root parameters under aluminum stress due to the observed obtuse angle between them, indicating that selection for a lower number of leaves under aluminum stress can improve seed yield. Similar findings have been reported by Ojo and Ayuba (2016) using correlation analysis. In this study, the tendency of traits in discriminating accessions in the right and the left-hand direction of the biplots depended on whether they had strong positive associations or negative associations as reported by Atnaf *et al.* (2017).

Conclusion

The present study has established that there is sufficient variability and heritability of growth, root, and yield parameters of cowpea accessions screened in pots under aluminum stress. The observed genetic variability among accessions could be exploited for developing tolerant lines through hybridization. The tolerance indices technique based on multiple quantitative traits is effective at identifying aluminum tolerant accessions.

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Table 1. Selected cowpea accessions

Accession ID	Tolerance for germination parameters	Code	Accession ID	Tolerance for germination parameters	Code
TVu-199	Highly susceptible	AC01	TVu-241	Highly tolerant	AC06
TVu-207	Moderately susceptible	AC02	IT98K-205-8	Moderately susceptible	AC07
TVu-218	Moderately tolerant	AC03	IT98K-555-1	Moderately tolerant	AC08
TVu-235	Moderately tolerant	AC04	TVu-4886	Moderately susceptible	AC09
TVu-236	Moderately tolerant	AC05	TVu-9256	Highly tolerant	AC10

Table 2. Effect of aluminum treatment on growth and yield traits of accessions of cowpea under aluminum stress

Treatment	EM (%)	PH (cm)	NL	DFF	PDP	SPP	SDPL	SDYPL (g)	NRT	RTL (cm)	DWR (g)
Control	89.33b	13.06a	6.45a	54.11a	11.30a	7.65a	82.39a	10.74a	12.03a	16.66b	0.74b
50 μ m	67.33a	12.59a	6.98ab	51.95a	10.30a	8.51a	84.03a	11.37a	11.81a	15.70b	0.60a
100 μ m	62.67a	12.39a	7.26b	52.58a	10.67a	8.17a	91.05a	10.94a	12.54a	13.80a	0.55a
200 μ m	60.00a	12.49a	7.42b	53.33a	11.10a	8.02a	88.06a	11.82a	11.96a	13.77a	0.77b
$\pm$ SE	4.27	0.31	0.22	0.82	0.45	0.39	5.79	0.8	0.29	0.36	0.03

Means followed by the same alphabets within a column are not significantly different from one another at $p \leq 0.05$ using DMRT; SE: Standard error. EM: Emergence percentage; PH: Plant height; NL: Number of leaves per plant; DFF: Number of days to first flowering; PDP: Number of pods per plant; SPP: Number of seeds per pod; SDPL: Number of seeds per plant; SDYPL: Seed yield per plant; NRT: Number of roots per plant; RTL: Root length per plant; DWR: Dry weight of roots.

Table 3. Estimates of genetic parameters of growth and yield traits of accessions of cowpea under aluminum stress

Trait	GM	σ_G^2	σ_P^2	σ_E^2	σ_{GT}^2	GCV (%)	PCV (%)	H ² (%)	GAM (%)
EM	69.83	138.06	163.98	546.67	-78.56	16.83	18.33	84.19	31.79
PH	12.63	1.09	1.25	2.92	-0.35	8.27	8.85	87.20	15.87
NL	7.03	1.78	1.95	1.41	0.21	18.98	19.86	91.28	37.52
DFF	52.99	9.09	10.16	19.93	-2.38	5.69	6.02	89.47	11.08
PDP	10.85	6.01	7.21	6.10	10.09	22.62	24.77	57.98	29.53
SPP	8.08	4.18	5.10	4.44	2.21	25.30	27.94	81.96	47.15
SDPL	86.38	632.04	1014.91	1005.75	119.24	29.10	36.88	62.28	47.31
SDYPL	11.22	8.31	11.88	19.03	7.91	25.72	30.75	69.95	44.26
NRT	12.09	5.76	7.21	2.49	4.95	19.85	22.21	79.89	36.48
RTL	14.98	9.16	12.02	3.93	10.16	20.20	23.14	76.14	36.30
DWR	0.67	0.04	0.05	0.03	0.03	29.85	33.37	80.00	55.90

GM: Grand mean; σ_G^2 : Genotypic variance; σ_P^2 : Phenotypic variance; σ_E^2 : Error variance; σ_{GT}^2 : Genotype $\times$ treatment variance; EM: Emergence percentage; PH: Plant height; NL: Number of leaves per plant; DFF: Number of days to first flowering; PDP: Number of pods per plant; SPP: Number of seeds per pod; SDPL: Number of seeds per plant; SDYPL: Seed yield per plant; NRT: Number of roots per plant; RTL: Root length per plant; DWR: Dry weight of roots. GCV: Genotypic coefficient of variation; PCV: Phenotypic coefficient of variation; H²: broad sense heritability; GAM: Genetic advance as a percent of the mean. EM: Emergence percentage; PH: Plant height; NL: Number of leaves per plant; DFF: Number of days to first flowering; PDP: Number of pods per plant; SPP: Number of seeds per pod; SDPL: Number of seeds per plant; SDYPL: Seed yield per plant; NRT: Number of roots per plant; RTL: Root length per plant; DWR: Dry weight of roots.

Table 4. Aluminum tolerance indices and (ranks) based on growth and yield traits of accessions of cowpea under aluminum stress

Accession	EMI	PHI	NLI	DFFI	PDPI	SPPI	SDPLI	SDYPLI	NRTI
AC01	0.86 (4)	1.35 (1)	1.47 (4)	0.89 (4)	0.99 (5)	0.49 (8)	0.54 (9)	0.65 (9)	0.61 (8)
AC02	0.59 (9)	1.15 (2)	1.60 (2)	0.85 (1)	1.16 (3)	0.66 (5)	0.87 (6)	1.05 (4)	0.40 (9)
AC03	0.69 (6)	0.85 (6)	0.61 (9)	0.97 (5)	1.13 (4)	2.17 (1)	2.69 (1)	2.09 (1)	1.46 (1)
AC04	0.95 (2)	1.01 (5)	0.75 (8)	1.06 (7)	0.98 (6)	1.41 (3)	1.55 (2)	1.54 (2)	1.42 (2)
AC05	0.89 (3)	1.07 (3)	0.77 (7)	1.19 (9)	0.49 (9)	1.71 (2)	1.07 (4)	0.87 (6)	1.29 (3)
AC06	0.82 (5)	0.80 (7)	0.59 (10)	1.16 (8)	0.69 (7)	1.41 (3)	1.09 (3)	1.22 (3)	1.08 (5)
AC07	0.22 (10)	0.76 (9)	0.99 (6)	1.02 (6)	0.45 (10)	1.41 (3)	0.66 (8)	0.65 (9)	1.03 (6)
AC08	0.97 (1)	0.78 (8)	1.59 (3)	0.87 (2)	1.28 (2)	0.52 (6)	0.72 (7)	0.83 (7)	1.14 (4)
AC09	0.62 (7)	1.03 (4)	2.12 (1)	0.87 (2)	1.84 (1)	0.51 (7)	1.03 (5)	1.04 (5)	1.08 (5)
AC10	0.61 (8)	0.85 (6)	1.12 (5)	0.88 (3)	0.63 (8)	1.07 (4)	0.72 (7)	0.72 (8)	0.85 (7)
GM	0.72	0.97	1.16	0.98	0.97	1.13	1.09	1.07	1.04

GM: Grand mean; EMI: Emergence percentage index; PHI: Plant height index; NLI: Number of leaves per plant index; DFFI: Number of days to first flowering index; PDPI: Number of pods per plant index; SPPI: Number of seeds per pod index; SDPLI: Number of seeds per plant index; SDYPLI: Seed yield per plant index; NRTI: Number of roots per plant index, RTLI: Root length per plant index; DWRI: Dry weight of roots index. $\bar{R}$: Rank sum; $\bar{R}$: Mean ranks; σ_R : Standard deviation of ranks.

Fig. 1. Bi-plots of accessions of cowpea under aluminum stress.